

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN ISLAMIC LAW AND ITS IMAGES

مفهوم الإعلام الاجتماعي في الشريعة الإسلامية وصوره

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Abstract

Topics related to the media today are among the topics worthy of study and care, as the media occupies a large and influential space in various fields of life. Perhaps social media is one of the most prominent types of media in terms of influence and importance, as it is based on transmitting news and information from the community to the community itself, to achieve one of the purposes of informing, guiding or guiding through its various means such as clubs, forums, places of worship, social networks, newspapers and books. The media directed to a particular place, group, or segment of society is considered its social media, such as the media directed to the community of a particular city or a segment such as women, or a group such as the disabled. Whereas social media is of such vitality and importance; This topic has been allocated according to the requirements of the study. In this study, I dealt with the subject of social media provisions and controls through Islamic law

The study was divided into two sections:

The first topic: the concept of social media in Islamic law.

The second topic: social media images in the light of Islamic law.

Whereas social media is of such vitality and importance; A separate chapter is devoted to this topic as required by the study requirements. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: pictures, media, social, Sharia, Islamic law.

ملخص البحث

تعد الموضوعات المتعلقة بالإعلام في وقتنا الحاضر من الموضوعات الجديرة بالدراسة والعناية، حيث يشغل الإعلام حيزًا كبيرًا ومؤثرًا في مختلف ميادين الحياة. ولعل الإعلام الاجتماعي هو أحد أبرز أنواع الإعلام من جهة التأثير والأهمية، حيث يركز على نقل الأخبار والمعلومات من المجتمع إلى المجتمع نفسه، لتحقيق غرض من الأغراض الإخبارية أو التوجيهية أو الإرشادية عبر وسائله المتنوعة كالنوادي والملتقيات ودور العبادة وشبكات التواصل الاجتماعي والصحف والكتب. ويعتبر الإعلام الموجه إلى مكان أو فئة أو شريحة معينة من شرائح المجتمع هو إعلامها الاجتماعي، كإعلام الموجه لمجتمع مدينة معينة أو شريحة كالنساء، أو فئة كالمعاقين. ولما كان الإعلام الاجتماعي بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. وانني إذ تناولت في هذه الدراسة موضوع أحكام الإعلام الاجتماعي وضوابطه من خلال الشريعة الإسلامية وقد قسمت الدراسة إلى مبحثين:

المبحث الأول: مفهوم الإعلام الاجتماعي في الشريعة الإسلامية.

المبحث الثاني: صور الإعلام الاجتماعي في ضوء الشريعة الإسلامية.

ولما كان الإعلام الاجتماعي بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت فصلاً مستقلاً في هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعاً لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: صور، الإعلام، الاجتماعي، الشريعة، الإسلامية.

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN ISLAMIC LAW AND ITS IMAGES

Social media can be defined in Islamic law as: “media based on providing people with information and firm facts, on the basis of building societies and the fixed values of individuals, and organizing inter-relationships between people in a way that achieves happiness and stability for individuals and societies”.

THE FIRST REQUIREMENT: SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE HOLY QUR’AN AND ITS IMAGES

Social media in the Holy Qur’an means: Qur’anic media, which aims to introduce the foundations of building society in Islam, such as belief, faith, rituals, worship, ideas and Islamic community concepts, Islamic community feelings, morals and virtues, and care for the development of social sense among members of society. The high humaneness of society in Islam as knowledge, work and social solidarity.

SOCIAL MEDIA IMAGES IN THE HOLY QUR’AN:

We will try to highlight some images of social media by narrating some verses that concerned societal issues and gave effective solutions and enacted effective rulings. Where the warning came in the Holy Qur’an against many moral and behavioral crimes, the most prominent and most heinous of which was the crime of

In the noble hadith, there is an indication of the virtue of helping the Muslim, relieving him of distress, and covering his slips. It includes the detection and relief of distress, whether the one who removed it with his money, prestige, or assistance. It appears that it includes those who removed it with his reference, opinion and significance. As for the covering that is referred to in the hadith, what is meant by it is covering people with appearances and the like, who are not known to be harmful and corrupt.

The laws, laws, and directives that seek to establish moral rules for human behavior in society are also evident in this great hadith, with the aim of behavioral and spiritual advancement, as linking every act with an unparalleled divine reward, just as he linked relieving distress in this world to a reward, which is breathing it in the hereafter. Insolvent may God facilitate in this world and the hereafter.

3. The Muslim community's dependence on this world is one of the reasons for the enemies' domination over it:

On the authority of Thawban, may God be pleased with him, he said: The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "The nations are about to be summoned over you as the eaters are invited to their bowl." Someone said: Who are we few on that day? He said: "Indeed, you are many on that day, but you are like the scum of a torrent, and God will remove the fear of you from the chests of your enemy, and God will cast weakness into your hearts." Someone said: O Messenger of God, what is weakness? He said: "Love of the world and hatred of death." That is, the sects of disbelief and nations of misguidance are close to inviting one another to fight the Muslims, break their thorns, plunder their possessions and plunder their wealth, just as people squabble and resolve to eat without any objection or fatigue. Then the Companions ask: Is this hypocrisy due to the small number of Muslims on that day? So the answer is that they are many, but they are like the foam and dirt of a torrent, and likening them to it because of their lack of courage and their lowness, and that God will remove from their enemy fear and terror from them, and will throw them and afflict them with weakness.

4. Urging the society to protect and immunize it from suspicions:

On the authority of Al-Nu'man bin Bashir, may God be pleased with him, who said: I heard the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, say: "The permissible is clear, and the forbidden is clear, and between them are ambiguous matters that many people do not know about. The forbidden, like a shepherd grazing around a fever, about to graze in it. But every king has a fever, except that God protects what he has forbidden. Except that in the body is a piece of flesh, if it is good, the whole body is good, and if it is corrupt, and it is the whole body."

Its meaning: that the halal and the haraam are two things that are apparent in their eyes and describe them with their apparent evidence, and between them are matters that have become similar from two opposing sides, many people do not know whether it is halal or what is forbidden? Whoever is wary of these doubts and warns against them has cleared his religion of any shortcomings, and protected his honor from being challenged, because he who is not known to avoid suspicions will not be safe from those who criticize him, and in the hadith there is evidence that whoever does not fear suspicion in his earnings and livelihood; He offered himself to challenge it, and this is an indication of preserving religious matters and observing chivalry, and whoever falls into these suspicions falls into the forbidden or close; Like a shepherd who grazes his sheep in places that are forbidden or prohibited or belong to owners who threaten those who graze in them without their permission with severe punishment, so the Prophet, peace and blessings of God be upon him, likened them to what is well known to them, so the fearful of punishment who is watching the owner's satisfaction is far from that fever lest his livestock fall into something of it after him He surrenders to him even if he is very careful, and is not afraid of the observer near him and grazing from his sides; But he is not safe from falling into the forbidden without testing him, so he does not have the power to fall into it, for God Almighty is truly the King and the protector of his prohibitions.

5. Directing care for the weak and needy, and urging social solidarity:

On the authority of Abu Hurairah, on the authority of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, he said: "The one who strives for the widow and the needy is like the one who strives in the way of God - and I think he said - and like the one who rises and does not give up, and like the fasting person who does not break his fast." What is meant by the courier here is the seeker of sustenance, the one who earns them, the worker for their provisions, and the widow who has no husband, whether she is married or not, and it was said that she is the one who left her husband.

On the authority of Abu Hurairah also, he said: The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "Oh God, I condemn the rights of the two weak ones: the orphan and the woman." That is, it is

more difficult for people to forfeit their right, and it is more difficult for them to do so. It is intended to witness the Almighty in conveying that judgment to them.

A widow without assistance will bring up her children without a father to support them, and they will suffer poverty, deteriorating living conditions, and perhaps deviation, and chaos and destruction will prevail in society as a result, especially since death is one of the laws of God Almighty that revolves around all of His creation. as well as an orphan, if he is left without bail or community assistance; it will sooner or later deviate towards theft and criminality; Thus, it becomes a tool of demolition and sabotage that causes chaos in society, disturbing its peace and violating its security and peace.

Conclusion:

The current study reached a number of results, which are:

1. Definitions of the concept of social media fluctuate between limiting it to the generality of what is provided by electronic social media, and the generality of what is issued by the media in a society.
2. There are many legal controls and provisions that should be observed and adhered to in the means, messages and topics of social media by including them in binding legal articles regulating media work.
3. The most prominent problems of social media are the weak coordination and cooperation between the relevant parties, the lack of awareness among members of the communities of its importance and its impact on their lives, in addition to the difficulty of controlling and censoring its contents and contents.

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() They differed about his name and the name of his father over eighteen sayings, the most famous of which is Abd Shams Ibn Amer. He was called in Islam Abdullah, and he had a small kitten, so he was named after her. He came to Medina in the year seven and the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, was in Khaybar; He traveled to Khaybar until he came with the Messenger of God, may God bless him

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() Mawla of the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and his name: Thawban bin Bajad, and it was said: Ibn Jahdur, nicknamed Abu Abdullah. He is from Sa'd al-Ash'ir from Manhaj. The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, bought him and freed him. He passed away in Egypt in the year (54 AH), and witnessed its conquest. See: See: Ibn al-Atheer, Ali Ibn Abi Karam (630 AH) The Lion of the Forest in the Knowledge of the Companions, (1409 AH - 1998 AD) Dar al-Fikr, Beirut, previous reference 1/269.

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() Al-Nu'man bin Bashir bin Saad bin Tha'labah bin Jalas bin Zaid bin Malik bin Thalabah bin Ka'b bin Al-Khazraj Al-Ansari Al-Khazraji, Abu Abdullah Al-Madani for him and his parents accompanied him and his mother Amra bin Rawahah, narrated on the authority of the Prophet, peace be upon him, and on the authority of his uncle Abdullah bin Rawahah and Omar And Aisha and others, and he was the first child born in the Ansar after the advent of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, according to most, he was killed in the year 566.

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() That is: it is more difficult for people to forfeit their rights and more stressful for them in that, and what is meant is His testimony, the Most High, in conveying that judgment to them. See: Al-Sindi, Muhammad bin Abd al-Hadi (1138 AH) Kifayat al-Hajja explaining Sunan Ibn Majah, Dar al-Jeel, Beirut 2/393.

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